

**NATIONAL LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK FOR SOCIAL PROTECTION OF
VICTIMS OF VIOLENCE**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the national legislative framework for social protection of victims of violence, mechanisms for ensuring their rights and freedoms, the activities of state bodies and social institutions in this area. It also discusses the current legislative documents on the prevention of violence, assistance to victims and their rehabilitation, and their practical significance.

Keywords: violence, social protection, national legislation, victim, prevention, rehabilitation, protection order, domestic violence, human rights

**НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬНАЯ БАЗА СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ
ЖЕРТВ НАСИЛИЯ**

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется национальная законодательная база социальной защиты жертв насилия, механизмы обеспечения их прав и свобод, деятельность государственных органов и социальных институтов в этой области. Также рассматриваются действующие законодательные документы по предотвращению насилия, оказанию помощи жертвам и их реабилитации, а также их практическое значение.

Ключевые слова: насилие, социальная защита, национальное законодательство, жертва, предотвращение, реабилитация, охранный ордер, домашнее насилие, права человека

Today, violence is one of the most pressing social problems. In particular, the increasing number of cases of domestic violence, violence against women and children creates the need to improve the social protection system in society.

According to data published by the WHO, approximately one third (30%) of women worldwide have experienced physical or sexual violence in their lifetime. In addition, data show that more than 1 billion children worldwide are exposed to physical, emotional or sexual violence every year. In this context, the formation of an effective national legislative framework for the protection and support of persons subjected to violence is of great importance.[2]

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the protection of human rights and freedoms is guaranteed at the level of the Constitution, which recognizes the honor and dignity of the person as a supreme value and states that no one may be subjected to torture, violence, other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.[1]

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing large-scale reforms aimed at protecting women and children from violence. In particular, the Law "On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" (No. O'PG-561, 2019) is of great importance in this regard.

The purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of protecting women from all forms of harassment and violence. Article 3 of this Law classifies the following types of violence:

- physical violence
- psychological violence

- economic violence
- sexual violence

This classification serves as an important tool in identifying violence and taking action against it.[3]

In addition, this article defines the protection order, one of the important means of protecting victims of violence in our national legislation, as follows: “a protection order is a document that provides state protection to a victim of oppression and violence, and causes the application of measures of influence established by this Law against a person or a group of persons who oppress or commit violence against women.”

A protection order imposes certain restrictions on the perpetrator of violence, including a ban on approaching, communicating with, or being in the same area as the victim.

Article 61 of the Law defines the powers of the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of protecting women from oppression and violence.

In addition, in our country, great attention is paid to protecting children from oppression and physical violence, and our government is adopting many laws and resolutions. In particular, the legal basis for the rights of the child and their guarantees is reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law “On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child”, the Law “On Guardianship and Guardianship Bodies”, and a number of other legislative acts.[4]

These official documents define the priority areas of state policy, such as

- ensuring the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of the child;
- protecting the life, health and dignity of the child;
- preventing his or her discrimination;
- promoting the physical, intellectual, spiritual and moral development of the younger generation.

In addition, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'PYK-996 of November 14, 2024 was adopted. The purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of protecting children from all forms of violence. This Law consists of 51 articles, and the law clearly defines the concept of violence against children. This law, which aims to comprehensively protect children, aims to ensure a prosperous future for the younger generation of our country.[5]

Rehabilitation centers also play an important role in the system of social protection of persons subjected to violence. In Uzbekistan, women's support centers, "Inson" social service centers, and various non-governmental organizations operate, providing free psychological, legal, and social assistance to victims. These centers provide services based on an individual approach by specialists, ensuring the reintegration of victims of violence into society. In addition, the opportunity to receive prompt advice and assistance through hotlines and online platforms has been created.

The fight against violence is not limited to legal measures, but also includes comprehensive preventive work. To this end, educational work is being carried out among the population in educational institutions, in the mahalla system and through the media. Increasing the legal literacy of the population, promoting the ideas of gender equality and creating a healthy family environment are important factors in preventing violence.

Cooperation between state bodies also increases the effectiveness of this system. Internal affairs bodies, the judicial and prosecutorial systems, health institutions and mahalla institutions work in close cooperation, implementing comprehensive measures to identify cases of violence, eliminate them and protect victims. For example, internal affairs bodies promptly consider appeals about violence and, if necessary, take legal action.

However, despite the current achievements, some problems remain. In particular, the concealment of cases of violence, the underdevelopment of social services in some regions, and the legal and other problems of the population are among the urgent problems in this area. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen preventive work, improve the skills of specialists, and expand the infrastructure of social services in the future.

In conclusion, the national legislative framework for social protection of persons subjected to violence is gradually improving in Uzbekistan. The laws being adopted, the mechanisms being created, and the practical measures being implemented are helping to reduce these problems. In the future, more effective results can be achieved by further developing this system, widely introducing international experience, and forming an intolerant attitude towards violence in society.

References

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